

8 week report on study of Integral equation and numerical computation using various techniques

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Abstract

The study over the period of 8 weeks begins with a introduction to integral equations,their types that is Volterra and Fredholm,their various methods of solutions including exact, approximate and numerical methods of solutions.Finally,the study turns to different techniques that could be used to approximate the solutions at different points within the given range.In this,the exact solution is obtained using the appropriate method as the selection was done in such a way that the exact solution was available and then again a method was applied to get the approximate solution.Finally the two values obtained were compared.The computations were done using a software Mathematica(version 7).

Contents

1 Integral equation,Their origin and classification

1.1 Introduction

An integral equation is an equation in which unknown function $u(x)$ appears under the integral sign.A general example of an integral equation

$$u(x) = f(x) + \int_a^b K(x,t)u(t)dt$$
$$a < x < b$$
$$a < t < b$$

where $K(x,t)$ is a function of two variables called the kernel or nucleus of the integral equation.Some of the problems have their direct representation appear directly, and in a very natural way,in terms of integral

equations. Other problems, whose direct representation is in terms of differential equations and their auxiliary conditions may also be reduced to integral equations.

1.2 Examples of problems as Integral Equations

For examples, the Integral equation in $u(x)$

$$u(x) = \int_0^x K(x,t)u(t)dt$$

relates the present state to the accumulation (integral) of what had happened at all the previous values $u(t)$ from $t=0$ to $t=x$

1.2.1 Human Population

Let the number of people at time $t=0$ be n_0 . If we look at the survival table, we find there is some sort of a survival function $f(t)$ which gives the fraction of people surviving to age t . It is assumed that these people are either male or female. The surviving population $n_s(t)$ at time is given by

$$n_s(t) = n_0 f(t)$$

If children are born at an average rate $r(t)$ then in a particular time interval $\delta_i \tau$ about the time τ , there are $r(\tau_i) \delta_i \tau$ children added who, if they survive, will be of age $(t - \tau)$ at time t . Let f be the survival function. Thus, the number of people added through new births which, if passed to the limit, becomes the integral

$$b(t) = \int_0^t f(t - \tau) r(\tau) d\tau$$

if this is added to $n_s(t)$, we get the total population at time t

$$n(t) = n_0 f(t) + k \int_0^t f(t - \tau) n(\tau) d\tau$$

which is a Volterra integral equation of the second type in $n(t)$

1.2.2 Periodicity in the surge of Birthrates

Let us assume there are (b_0) women present at the initial time $t=0$ and that they will give birth to a female child at a rate $h(t)$ per year. Then their contribution $g(t)$ to the female birth rate at time t is given by

$$g(t) = b_0 h(t)$$

To find the birthrate $b(t)$ at time t , we must add to this the contribution to birthrates of girls born at time $\tau > 0$ when they are at age τ in the range of childbearing age $\alpha < \tau < \beta$. Girls born at time $(t - \tau)$ will at future time t belong to the birthrate $b(t - \tau)$. Let the probability of a girl living to age τ is $l(\tau)$ and the probability of the girl at this age giving birth to a female child in a time interval $\delta\tau$ is $m(\tau)\delta\tau$. Then the final birth rate at time t is given by the integral equation

$$b(t) = b_0 h(t) + \int_{\alpha}^{\beta} b(t - \tau) l(\tau) m(\tau) d\tau$$

1.2.3 Biological species living together

Consider the two species with number $n_1(t)$ and $n_2(t)$, respectively, present at time t . If the two species are left separate, it is reasonable to assume that their rate of change dn/dt is proportional to $n(t)$, the number found at time t ,

$$\frac{dn}{dt} = \alpha(t)n$$

Here α is the proportionality constant or the coefficient of increase ($\alpha > 0$) or decrease ($\alpha < 0$). Let us assume that the first species is increasing with coefficient of increase $k_1 (k_1 > 0)$ and the second species is decreasing with coefficient of decrease $-k_2 (k_2 > 0)$. If the two species are introduced together then k_1 would modify to

$$k_1' = k_1 - \gamma_1 n_2(t)$$

where γ_1 is a proportionality constant which depends on the first species. The actual decrease in k_1 is due not only to the presence (feeding) of the second species $n_2(t)$ at the present time t but also to all previous presences (feedings) of $n_2(\tau)$ for the whole time interval $t - T_0 < \tau < t$ where T_0 is the finite heredity duration of both species. If in addition to the presence γ_1 factor we have the record of its rate of decrease as $f_1(\tau)$ in previous times $t - T_0 < \tau < t$, then the decrease in k_1 at time t , due to the decrease in the time interval $\delta\tau$, is $-f_1(t - \tau)n_2(\tau)\delta\tau$ and vice versa for species n_2 . The final expressions are-

$$\frac{dn_1}{dt} = n_1(t)[k_1 - \gamma_1 n_2(t) - \int_{t-T_0}^t f_1(t - \tau)n_2(\tau)d\tau]$$

$$\frac{dn_2}{dt} = n_2(t)[-k_2 - \gamma_2 n_1(t) - \int_{t-T_0}^t f_2(t - \tau)n_1(\tau)d\tau]$$

These are in fact a system of integro-differential equations.

1.2.4 Mortality of Equipment and rate of replacement

This is a problem of finding the rate dr/dt at which equipment should be replaced to keep a specified number $f(t)$ in operating condition at any time t . We first assume that we have $s(t)$, the function that determines the number of pieces of new equipment bought at $t=0$ that survives to time t . If we start with $f(0)$ as the number of new equipment at time $t=0$ then, due to loss or wear, only the fraction $f(0)s(t)$ will survive till time t . To keep a specified number of equipment larger than $f(0)s(t)$ at time t we must continuously add equipment to the desired rate from $t=0$ to time t . If the desired rate of replacement at which we must add new equipment at time τ is $dr(\tau)/d\tau$. Hence the rate of replacement is given by-

$$r(t) = \int_0^t s(t - \tau) \frac{dr}{d\tau} d\tau$$

Thus we obtain the total number of pieces of equipment in operating condition at time t

$$f(t) = f(0)s(t) + \int_0^t s(t - \tau) \frac{dr}{d\tau} d\tau$$

1.3 Multiple Integral reduced to Single Integrals

The double integral can be reduced to a single integral

$$\int_a^x \int_a^y F(t) dt d\psi = \int_a^y (x - t) F(t) dt$$

This can be simply proved by changing the order of integral

$$\begin{aligned} \int_a^x \int_a^y F(t) dt dy &= \int_a^x F(t) \int_t^x dy dt \\ &= \int_a^x (x - t) F(t) dt \end{aligned}$$

1.4 Abel's problem and its solution using a elementary method

1.4.1 Sliding Along a wire: Abel's problem

One of the earliest problems formulated as an integral equations was Abel's problem. It describes the shape of a wire $\phi(y)$ in a vertical plane along which a bead must descend (under the influence of gravity) a distance y_0 in a predetermined time $f(y_0)$. This is represented by Abel's integral equation in $\phi(y)$

$$-\sqrt{2g}f(y_0) = \int_0^{y_0} \frac{\phi(y) dy}{\sqrt{y_0 - y}}$$

1.4.2 Generalized Abel's problem

Type-1-a

$$\int_a^x \frac{\psi(t)}{(x - t)^\alpha} dt = f(x)$$

$$f(a) = 0, x > t, 0 < \alpha < 1$$

Type-2-a

$$\int_x^b \frac{\psi(t)}{(t - x)^\alpha} dt = f(x)$$

$$f(b) = 0, x < t, 0 < \alpha < 1$$

Type-1-b

$$\int_a^x \frac{\psi(t)}{(h(x) - h(t))^\alpha} dt = f(x)$$

$$f(a) = 0, a < x < b, 0 < \alpha < 1$$

where $h(x)$ is monotonic increasing in (a, b)

Type-1-b

$$\int_x^b \frac{\psi(t)}{(h(t) - h(x))^\alpha} dt = f(x)$$

$$f(b) = 0, 0 < \alpha < 1$$

where $h(x)$ is monotonic increasing in (a, b)

1.4.3 Solution of generalized Abel's problem using elementary method

$$\int_a^x \frac{\psi(t)}{(x-t)^\alpha} dt = f(x)$$

$$f(a) = 0, x > t, 0 < \alpha < 1$$

Multiply both sides by $\frac{1}{(y-x)^{1-\alpha}}$ and integrate with respect to x between a to y

$$\begin{aligned} \int_a^y \frac{f(x)}{(y-x)^{1-\alpha}} dx &= \int_a^y \frac{1}{(y-x)^{1-\alpha}} \left[\int_a^x \frac{\psi(t)}{(x-t)^\alpha} dt \right] dx \\ &= \int_a^y \psi(t) \left[\int_a^x \frac{1}{(x-t)^\alpha (y-x)^{1-\alpha}} dt \right] dx \end{aligned}$$

calculating

$$\int_a^x \frac{\psi(t)}{(x-t)^\alpha (y-x)^{1-\alpha}} dt$$

through change of order, substituting $x = y \sin^2 \theta + t \cos^2 \theta$ and using the property

$$B(m, n) = 2 \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sin^{2m-1} \theta \cos^{2n-1} \theta d\theta = \frac{\Gamma(m) \Gamma(n)}{\Gamma(m+n)}$$

we get

$$\int_a^y \psi(t) dt = \frac{\sin(\pi\alpha)}{\pi} \int_a^y \frac{f(x)}{(y-x)^{1-\alpha}} dx$$

Differentiating Both sides

$$\psi(y) = \frac{\sin(\pi\alpha)}{\pi} \frac{d}{dy} \int_a^y \frac{f(x)}{(y-x)^{1-\alpha}} dx$$

In similar way solution of problem-2 can be calculated.

1.5 Initial value problems reduced to Volterra Integral Equations

$$\frac{d^2y}{dx^2} = \lambda y(x) + g(x)$$

(a)

$$y(0) = 1$$

(1)

$$y'(0) = 1$$

(2)

we let

$$\frac{d^2y}{dx^2} = F(x)$$

Integrating twice we obtain

$$y(x) = \int_0^x \int_0^\xi F(t) dt d\xi + c_1x + c_2$$

Converting to single integral

$$y(x) = \int_0^x (x - \xi)F(\xi)d\xi + c_1x + c_2$$

Applying initial conditions

$$c_2 = 1$$

$$c_2 = 0$$

Thus,we obtain

$$y(x) = 1 + \int_0^x (x - \xi)F(\xi)d\xi$$

(3)

Using (a) and (3),we have

$$F(x) = \frac{d^2y}{dx^2} = \lambda y(x) + g(x)$$

(4)

Substituting $F(x)$ from (4) in above equation (3)

$$y(x) = 1 + \lambda \int_0^x (x - \xi)y(\xi)d\xi + \int_0^x (x - \xi)g(\xi)d\xi$$

which is a Volterra integral equation of the second kind in $y(x)$.

1.6 Boundary value problems reduced to Fredholm Integral Equations

$$\frac{d^2y}{dx^2} + A(x)\frac{dy}{dx} + B(x)y = g(x)$$

$$y(a) = c_1$$

$$y(b) = c_2$$

It is represented by a Fredholm integral equation of the second kind

$$y(x) = f(x) + \int_a^b K(x, t)y(t)dt$$

where

$$f(x) = c_1 + \int_a^x (x-t)g(t)dt + \frac{x-a}{b-a}[c_2 - c_1 - \int_a^b (b-t)g(t)dt]$$

and

$$K(x, t) = \frac{(x-b)}{(b-a)}(A(t) - (a-t)[A'(t) - B(t)])$$

$x > t$

$$K(x, t) = \frac{(x-a)}{(b-a)}(A(t) - (b-t)[A'(t) - B(t)])$$

$x < t$

2 Volterra Integral Equations

2.1 Volterra Integral Equation of the second kind

2.1.1 Resolvent Kernel Method:Neumann Series

The method is demonstrated through application to a problem that I used afterwards in numerical computation

$$u(x) = x + 2 \int_0^x e^{x-t}u(t)dt$$

$$\lambda = 2$$

It has a resolvent kernel

$$K(x, t) = K_1(x, t) = e^{x-t}$$

Solution is of the form

$$u(x) = f(x) + \lambda \int_0^x \gamma(x, t; \lambda)f(t)dt$$

Here $f(x)=x$

$$K_2(x, t) = \int_t^x K(x, \xi)K_1(\xi, t)dt$$

On solving

$$= (x - t)e^{x-t}$$

$$K_n(x, t) = \int_t^x K(x, \xi)K_{n-1}(\xi, t)dt$$

I found

$$K_{n+1}(x, t) = \frac{(x - t)^n e^{x-t}}{n}$$

$$\gamma(x, t; \lambda) = K_1(x, t) + \lambda K_2(x, t) - - - - -$$

Thus, the solution is

$$u(x) = x + \frac{2}{9}e^{3x} - \frac{2}{9}(3x + 1)$$

2.1.2 Laplace Transform Method: Difference Kernel

This is again demonstrated with a help of a problem

$$y(x) = \cos x - x - 1 - \int_0^x (x - t)y(t)dt$$

Taking Laplace transform both sides

$$Y(s) = \frac{s}{s^2 + 1} - \frac{1}{s^2} - \frac{1}{s} - \frac{Y(s)}{s^2}$$

On solving

$$Y(s) = -\frac{s}{(s^2 + 1)^2} - \frac{1}{s^2 + 1}$$

Taking inverse Laplace transform

$$= -\sin x - \frac{x \sin x}{2}$$

The method can be also be applied to Integrodifferential equation which is of the form-

$$\frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} = f(x) + \int_0^x K(x, t)u(t)dt$$

this is because of the presence of the result that Laplace Transform of $\frac{d^2 y}{dx^2}$

$$= s^2 U(s) - su(0) - u'(0)$$

2.2 Volterra Integral Equation of the first kind

The Volterra Integral Equation of the first kind

$$f(x) = \lambda \int_0^x K(x, t)u(t)dt$$

can be reduced to Volterra integral equation of the second kind when $K(x, x) \neq 0$

On differentiating both sides with respect to x , we have

$$\frac{df}{dx} = \lambda \int_0^x \frac{\partial K(x, x)}{\partial x} u(t) dt + \lambda K(x, x) u(x)$$

This can be easily re-written as

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{\partial K(x, x)} \frac{df}{dx} - \int_0^x \frac{1}{K(x, x)} \frac{\partial K(x, t)}{\partial x} u(t) dt$$

if we let

$$g(x) = \frac{1}{\lambda K(x, x)} \frac{df}{dx}$$

and

$$H(x, t) = \frac{-1}{K(x, t)} \frac{\partial K(x, t)}{\partial x}$$
$$u(x) = g(x) + \int_0^x H(x, t) u(t) dt$$

This equation can be solved by using the methods that are used to solve Volterra equation of the second kind

3 Construction of the Green's function

The Green's function is one of the most important methods for solving boundary value problems associated with non-homogeneous ordinary or partial differential equations.

3.1 Construction of the Green's function

The method of variation of parameters is used here to construct the Green's function for non-homogeneous boundary problems.

Assuming the solution of non-homogeneous problem to be

$$u(x) = a_1(x)v_1(x) + a_2(x)v_2(x)$$

where the variable coefficient parameters $a_1(x)$ and $a_2(x)$ are to be determined via this method. Assuming that neither of the solutions $v_1(x)$ or $v_2(x)$ satisfies boundary conditions which are-

$$\alpha_1 y(a) + \alpha_2 y'(a) = 0$$

(a)

$$\beta_1 y(a) + \beta_2 y'(a) = 0$$

(b)

The non-homogeneous differential equation is-

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left[r(x) \frac{du}{dx} \right] + [q(x) + \lambda \rho(x)] u(x) \equiv Lu = f(x)$$
$$a < x < b$$

Taking derivative of $u(x)$

$$u'(x) = a_1(x)v_1'(x) + a_2(x)v_2'(x) + a_1'(x)v_1(x) + a_2'(x)v_2(x)$$

As per the method the last two terms are assigned to zero

$$a_1'(x)v_1(x) + a_2'(x)v_2(x) = 0$$

(1)

Thus we get

$$u'(x) = a_1(x)v_1'(x) + a_2(x)v_2'(x)$$

Keeping the respective values in the equation $Lu=f(x)$

We get

$$a_1'(x)v_1'(x) + a_2'(x)v_2'(x) = \frac{f(x)}{r(x)}$$

Using the above equation and (1), We get

$$a_1'(x) = \frac{f(x)v_2(x)}{r(x)[v_2(x)v_1'(x) - v_1(x)v_2'(x)]}$$
$$a_2'(x) = \frac{f(x)v_1(x)}{r(x)[v_2'(x)v_1(x) - v_1'(x)v_2(x)]}$$

As L operator used here is a self-adjoint operator and moreover v_1 and v_2 are solutions of $Lu=0$ as well, Thus

$$0 = v_2 L v_1 - v_1 L v_2 = \frac{d}{dx} [r(x)[v_1(x)v_2'(x) - v_2(x)v_1'(x)]]$$

Thus

$$r(x)[v_1(x)v_2'(x) - v_2(x)v_1'(x)] = B = \text{constant}$$

Assuming that a_1 satisfies the boundary condition at $x=a$ and a_2 at $x=b$ we get,

$$a_1(x) = -\frac{1}{B} \int_a^x f(\xi)v_2(\xi)d\xi$$

$$a_2(x) = -\frac{1}{B} \int_x^b f(\xi)v_1(\xi)d\xi$$

Putting back in $u(x)$

$$u(x) = a_1(x)v_1(x) + a_2(x)v_2(x)$$

$$= -\frac{1}{B}v_1(x) \int_a^x f(\xi)v_2(\xi)d\xi - \frac{1}{B}v_2(x) \int_x^b f(\xi)v_1(\xi)d\xi$$

$$= -\int_a^b G(x, \xi)f(\xi)d\xi$$

where

$$G(x, \xi) = \frac{1}{B}v_1(x)v_2(\xi)$$

$$\xi \leq x \leq b$$

$$G(x, \xi) = \frac{1}{B}v_2(x)v_1(\xi)$$

$$a \leq x \leq \xi$$

3.2 Properties of the Green's function

(a)It is clear that the Green's function is symmetric,that is

$$G(x, \xi) = G(\xi, x)$$

This is a direct consequence of the operator L being self adjoint.

(b) $G(x, \xi)$ is clearly continuous on the interval $a \leq x \leq b$; however, its derivative $\frac{\partial G(x, \xi)}{\partial x}$ has a jump discontinuity at $x = \xi$.

$$(c) \frac{\partial g(x, \xi)}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=\xi_+} - \frac{\partial g(x, \xi)}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=\xi_-} = -\frac{1}{r(\xi)}$$

where $r(x)$ is the coefficient of $u''(x)$

4 Fredholm Integral equation

An important condition,termed the regularity condition,for the development of the solution of the Fredholm integral equations is that the kernel $K(x,t)$ be square integrable in both x and t in the square

$(x, t) : a \leq x \leq b, a \leq t \leq b$ that is

$$\int_a^b \int_a^b |K(x, t)|^2 dx dt = B^2$$

is finite

4.1 Method of iterated kernels

The method here is demonstrated with the help of a problem that I also used in numerical computation.

$$u(x) = e^{-x} - \int_0^1 x e^t u(t) dt$$

$$K_2(x, y) = \int_0^1 K(x, t) K_1(t, y) dt = \int_0^t x e^t t e^y dt = x e^y$$

In the same way it was found

$$K_1(x, y) = K_2(x, y) \dots \dots = x e^y$$

thus solution is of the form

$$u(x) = f(x) + x \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \lambda^i \int_0^1 e^y f(y) dy$$

where

$$f(x) = e^{-x}$$

$$\lambda = -1$$

After putting the required values, we get

$$u(x) = e^{-x} - x/2$$

4.2 Fredholm Integral Equations with degenerate kernel

The method here is depicted with the help of a particular problem that I solved in the course of learning this method.

$$u(x) = x + \lambda \int_0^1 (x t^2 + x^2 t) u(t) dt$$

$$K(x, t) = x t^2 + x^2 t = \sum_{k=1}^2 a_k(x) b_k(t)$$

$$f_n = \int_0^1 b_1(t) f(t) dt$$

Thus

$$f_1 = \frac{1}{4}$$
$$f_1 = \frac{1}{3}$$

In similar way

$$a_{m,n} = \int_0^1 b_m(t)a_n(t)dt$$

From above

$$a_{11} = \frac{1}{4}$$
$$a_{12} = \frac{1}{5}$$
$$a_{21} = \frac{1}{3}$$
$$a_{22} = \frac{1}{4}$$

We know that $C = F + \lambda AC$ where

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 \\ c_2 \end{bmatrix}$$
$$F = \begin{bmatrix} f_1 \\ f_2 \end{bmatrix}$$
$$A = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{bmatrix}$$

Solving

$$c_1 = \frac{60 + \lambda}{240 - 120\lambda - \lambda^2}$$
$$c_1 = \frac{80}{240 - 120\lambda - \lambda^2}$$

Putting in

$$u(x) = f(x) + \lambda \sum_{k=1}^n c_k a_k(x)$$

we get

$$u(x) = \frac{(240 - 60\lambda)x + 80\lambda x^2}{240 - 120\lambda - \lambda^2}$$

$$240 - 120\lambda - \lambda^2 \neq 0$$

In case $240 - 120\lambda - \lambda^2 = 0$, the equation does not have a unique solution

It is zero for two values of λ .

Finding those two through method of Eigenvalue and Eigenfunction. The solution in that case is-

(a) for $\lambda = 4(15 - 4 * \sqrt{15})$

$$u(x) = 0.328x + 0.409x^2$$

(b) $\lambda = 4(15 + 4 * \sqrt{15})$

$$u(x) = 0.006x + 0.0066x^2$$

4.3 Fredholm Alternative

If the homogeneous integral equation

$$u(x) = \lambda \int_a^b K(x, \xi)u(\xi)d\xi$$

has only the trivial solution $u(x) \equiv 0$ than the corresponding non-homogeneous equation

$$u(x) = f(x) + \lambda \int_a^b K(x, \xi)u(\xi)d\xi$$

has one and only one solution. On the contrary, if the homogeneous equation has some nontrivial solution, then the non-homogeneous integral equation has either no solution or an infinity of solutions depending on the given function $f(x)$

4.4 Some other methods studied

4.4.1 (a) Approximating a kernel by a degenerate one

4.4.2 (b) Fredholm Integral Equations with degenerate kernel

4.4.3 (c) Rayleigh-Ritz method

4.4.4 (d) Method of Fredholm Resolvent kernel

4.4.5 (e) Approximation methods

5 Numerical Computation

Two methods were used in numerical computation. The exact solution was obtained by applying the appropriate method as the selection of problems was as such and then the values of the exact solution were

compared at different points from the values obtained by the approximate method

5.1 Method-1(Polynomial Expansion Method)

In this method,the required function is expanded in terms of a polynomial function such that-

$$u(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i x^i$$

The expansion was tested for various values of n. The first is a Volterra integral equation and second is a Fredholm integral equation.

5.1.1 Problem-1(Exact solution)

$$y(x) = \cos x - x - 1 - \int_0^x (x-t)y(t)dt$$

Taking Laplace transform both sides

$$Y(s) = \frac{s}{s^2 + 1} - \frac{1}{s^2} - \frac{1}{s} - \frac{Y(s)}{s^2}$$

On solving

$$y(s) = -\frac{s}{(s^2 + 1)^2} - \frac{1}{s^2 + 1}$$

Taking inverse Laplace transform

$$= -\sin x - \frac{x \sin x}{2}$$

5.1.2 Problem-1(Approximate solution)

The computation of unknowns was done by Collocation method by substituting the polynomial function in the given Integral equation.

(a) For n=3

$$y(x) = -x - (x^2)/2 + (x^3)/4$$

(b) For n=5

$$y(x) = -x - (x^2)/2 + (x^3)/3 + (x^4)/24$$

(c) For n=7

$$y(x) = -x - x^2/2 + x^3/6 + x^4/12 - x^5/120 - x^6/240 + x^7/5040$$

5.1.3 Problem-1(Comparison at different points)

(a)

$$n = 3$$

	x=0.1	x=0.3	x=0.5	x=0.7	x=0.9
Exact solutions	-0.100	-0.218	-0.599	-0.8700	-1.26
Approximate Solutions	-0.1045	-0.336	-0.597	-0.859	-1.21

(b)

$$n = 5$$

	x=0.1	x=0.3	x=0.5	x=0.7	x=0.9
Exact solutions	-0.100	-0.218	-0.599	-0.8700	-1.26
Approximate Solutions	-0.10084	-0.196	-0.602	-0.877	-1.29

(c)

$$n = 7$$

	x=0.1	x=0.3	x=0.5	x=0.7	x=0.9
Exact solutions	-0.100	-0.218	-0.599	-0.8700	-1.26
Approximate Solutions	-0.104	-0.338	-0.599	-0.863	-1.14

5.1.4 Conclusion

It is obvious that as n increases the results become more accurate.

5.1.5 Problem-2(Exact Solution)

$$u(x) = e^{-x} - \int_0^1 xe^t u(t) dt$$

$$K_2(x, y) = \int_0^1 K(x, t)K_1(t; y) dt = \int_0^t xe^t te^y dt = xe^y$$

In the same way it was found

$$K_1(x, y) = K_2(x, y) \dots \dots = xe^y$$

thus solution is of the form

$$u(x) = f(x) + x \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \lambda^i \int_0^1 e^y f(y) dy$$

where

$$f(x) = e^{-x}$$

$$\lambda = -1$$

After putting the required values, we get

$$u(x) = e^{-x} - x/2$$

5.1.6 Problem-2(Approximate Solution)

The computations of unknowns was done by Collocation method by substituting the polynomial function in the given Integral equation.

(a) For n=5

$$u(x) = 0.999993 - 1.4998x + 0.499917x^2 - 0.164107x^3 + 0.03752x^4 + 0.004835x^5$$

(b) For n=9

$$u(x) = 1 - 1.5x + 0.5x^2 - 0.1666x^3 + 0.0416661x^4 - 0.00833176x^5 + 0.00138609x^6 - 0.000195101x^7 + 0.00002227x^8 - 1.5957 \times 10^{-6}x^9$$

5.1.7 Problem-2(Comparison at different points)

(a)

$$n = 5$$

	x=0.1	x=0.3	x=0.5	x=0.7	x=0.9
Exact solutions	0.854837	0.590818	0.146585	0.356531	-0.0434
Approximate Solutions	0.854837	0.590816	0.146522	0.356515	-0.0435

(b)

$$n = 9$$

	x=0.1	x=0.3	x=0.5	x=0.7	x=0.9
Exact solutions	0.854837	0.590818	0.146585	0.356531	-0.0434
Approximate Solutions	0.854837	0.590818	0.146584	0.35651	-0.0435

5.1.8 Conclusion

It is obvious that as n increases the results become more accurate.

5.2 Method-2(based on the expansion in terms of Chebyshev polynomials)

In this method, the approximation is done using the ChebyshevU polynomial and the unknowns are found out by substituting the roots of ChebyshevT polynomial. If the degree of ChebyshevU polynomial used is n then ChebyshevT polynomial used is of degree $(n+1)$ as then there are $(n+1)$ unknowns including the constant.

$$U_n(x) = \frac{\sin(n+1)\theta}{\sin\theta}$$

where

$$x = \cos\theta$$

And

$$T_n(x) = \cos n\theta$$

where

$$x = \cos\theta$$

5.2.1 Exact Solution

$$u(x) = e^{-x} - \int_0^1 x e^t u(t) dt$$

$$K_2(x, y) = \int_0^1 K(x, t) K_1(t; y) dt = \int_0^t x e^t t e^y dt = x e^y$$

In the same way it was found

$$K_1(x, y) = K_2(x, y) \dots = x e^y$$

thus solution is of the form

$$u(x) = f(x) + x \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \lambda^i \int_0^1 e^y f(y) dy$$

where

$$f(x) = e^{-x}$$

$$\lambda = -1$$

After putting the required values, we get

$$u(x) = e^{-x} - x/2$$

5.2.2 Approximate solution

The calculation was done in the following way-

$$u(x) = e^{-x} - \int_0^1 x e^t u(t) dt$$
$$x = \frac{a+b}{2} + \frac{b-a}{2} y$$

(1)

$$t = \frac{a+b}{2} + \frac{b-a}{2} \tau$$

(2)

$$e^{-\left(\frac{1+y}{2}\right)} = \sum_{i=0}^n a_n A_n(y)$$

(3)

$$u(y) = a_n U_n(y)$$

(4)

The $A_n(y)$ was calculated and then a_n by using the $(n+1)^{th}$ $T_n(y)$ polynomial's roots and then keeping back in (4)

5.2.3 Comparison at different points

	x=0.2	x=0.3	x=0.4	x=0.5	x=0.6
Exact solutions	0.71	0.590	0.470	0.356531	0.248812
Approximate Solutions	0.62	0.510	0.447	0.356518	0.256312

6 Books and papers studied

6.1 Papers

(1)-On the methods of solutions of singular Integral equations.(By A.Chakrabarti and S.C Martha)

(2)-Techniques of solving the singular integral equations of first kind with a Cauchy kernel and application to some water waves(By Dr. B.N Mandal)

6.2 Books

- (1)-Introduction to integral equations with applications-By Abdul J.Jerri
- (2)-Linear Integral Equations-By Ram P.Kanwal
- (3)-Theory of functions of complex variables-By Narayan Shanti
- (4)-Integral Equations,By M. Petrowski